

Reproducibility of "PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference"

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The following paper is a short report about the reproducibility for "*PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference*" [3] published at SIGIR in 2022. The goal is to test this research paper for reproducibility.

Additional Key Words: recommendation system, emoji recommendation, deep learning.

1 Introduction

Emoji recommendation has emerged as a crucial task in assisting users in selecting appropriate emojis from a vast pool of candidates based on short text, such as tweets. Traditional emoji recommendation methods often lack personalization and overlook the historical information of users when suggesting emojis. In this paper, we focus on the reproducibility study of the paper titled "PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference" by Xuanzhi Zheng, Guoshuai Zhao, Li Zhu, and Xueming Qian [3]. Reproducibility studies play a crucial role in the scientific research landscape by independently evaluating and validating previously published work. This study aims to replicate the results presented in the original paper by recreating the experiments.

2 Original Experiment

In the paper, experiments are performed on two real-world datasets named Weibo and Twitter. The Weibo dataset comprises 1.53 million tweets from 89,600 users, with 50 unique emojis. The Twitter dataset includes 1.63 million tweets from 6,500 users, also with 50 unique emojis.

For experiments on the Weibo dataset, the Chinese BERT model is pre-trained and utilized. The model has a depth of 12, a word vector dimension of 768, and 12 multi-heads in attention. On the Twitter dataset, the BERT-Medium model is employed, featuring 8 layers, 512 hidden states, and 8 heads. The dimension of user preference representations is set to match that of word vectors.

Due to runtime memory constraints, the length of the user historical tweet list s is set to 4. Adam is used for gradient descent, with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-5} . Model training continues until the training iteration reaches the maximum epoch number or the training loss stops decreasing. The model with the best performance on the validation set is selected for testing. Evaluation metrics include Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and NDCG scores. The source code is available on GitHub.

Figure 1: Experimental results on Weibo Dataset

Methods	Kim-CNN	libFM	B-LSTM	DeepFM	mmGRU	CAPER	PERD
P@5	0.0849	0.0929	0.1054	0.1011	0.1302	0.1151	0.1242
R@5	0.4238	0.3687	0.3962	0.3765	0.5191	0.4472	0.5337
F@5	0.1415	0.1484	0.1665	0.1594	0.2082	0.1831	0.2016
P@10	0.0604	0.0632	0.0814	0.0741	0.0789	0.0817	0.0822
R@10	0.6043	0.5013	0.3136	0.5522	0.6291	0.6349	0.7051
F@10	0.1098	0.1122	0.1318	0.1307	0.1402	0.1448	0.1472
N@5	0.2903	0.3105	0.3187	0.2688	0.5024	0.3399	0.3886
N@10	0.3321	0.3593	0.3663	0.3287	0.5408	0.3932	0.4307

Figure 2: Experimental results on Twitter Dataset

Methods	Kim-CNN	libFM	B-LSTM	DeepFM	mmGRU	CAPER	PERD
P@5	0.0763	0.0798	0.0837	0.1098	0.0916	0.1357	0.1691
R@5	0.3816	0.3225	0.1896	0.4201	0.3473	0.5242	0.6407
F@5	0.1272	0.1279	0.1161	0.1741	0.1450	0.2148	0.2676
P@10	0.0521	0.0590	0.0585	0.0748	0.0601	0.0909	0.1026
R@10	0.5211	0.4769	0.2652	0.5725	0.4558	0.6884	0.7778
F@10	0.0948	0.1050	0.0959	0.1324	0.1063	0.1606	0.1814
N@5	0.2301	0.2566	0.0872	0.3332	0.2835	0.4352	0.5826
N@10	0.3022	0.3435	0.1359	0.3833	0.3230	0.4831	0.6168

3 Reproducibility

While reproducing the paper, a lot of errors occurred. To justify reproducibility, we used the proposed PRIMAD model by Braganholo et al. [1].

3.1 Platform

The author did not provide any information about the used platform for their experiments. There was no information about the used system and operating system they used to run the experiment. They did not give any description of how much RAM or what type of CPU they used. The paper did not mention

how much computational power is needed to run the experiment, nor how long the run-time of the experiment on the large datasets was.

3.2 Research Objective

They properly instructed their motivation for the model and how it compares against other baseline approaches. Showing, that the code can be useful in this setting of emoji recommendation, but not how the model applies to different problems. But if the code is executable, it can probably be re-purposed to a different setting.

3.3 Implementation

The authors provided the Python code of their proposed PERD model on GitHub [4]. Unfortunately, this code has many errors, which made the experiments very hard to reproduce. Following, are the major issues we encountered while working with their code.

Code versioning: The latest commit on the repository was in a merge state of two commits. Meaning, a lot of files had code from two different commits. The files contained the code of the preview from a work-in-progress merge conflict. To solve this problem, we had to choose which version of the code was the correct one and hope to choose the correct version of the file.

Library versions: Neither the paper nor the code on GitHub [4] provide any sort of description about the used Python version or the versions of used packages. Fortunately, they did not use many packages. The main dependency issue was with the correct version of *tensorflow* for the method *tensorflow.contrib*. To use the method *tensorflow.contrib* we had to use TensorFlow version 1.xx, which was compatible with Python version 3.7 or lower. The limitation to an older TensorFlow version caused another problem. Google Colab only allows version 2 or higher. This basically eliminated the option for us to use more computational power. Meaning, that we are limited to running experiments locally without having sufficient information about what kind of architecture they used in the paper.

Missing files: The project did not have the mentioned pre-trained BERT models included in the file structure. Also, they did not mention how the BERT models should be included in the code to ensure a smooth execution.

Missing description: There was no description of how to execute the code. They did not provide documentation about their code base and how to set up and run the project locally. A lot of the comments in the code were written in Chinese and English, further increasing the difficulty of the readability of the code base.

3.4 Method

They did not give any description of how they performed the train and test split of their datasets. So, there is no way to exactly reproduce their experiments and test their hypothesis on correctness.

3.5 Actor

The authors did not provide enough information to test their implementation and verify their results. There are no independent sources of verification, that the code in this paper is reproducible and if the results are correct.

3.6 Data

The datasets are neither available in their provided GitHub Repository [4] nor in referenced papers [2]. They only provided a small subset of the original Twitter dataset as sample-data in their project, without any description of how they used them or how they could be used by researchers to reproduce the results. The sample-data contains four pickled files with data about tweets, one-hot-encoded labels, ids and labels. With no description, it is hard to identify how to use the data. We assume the labels are the preselected subset of available recommendable emojis, one-hot-encoded labels are the emojis from historical tweets but transformed with one-hot-encoding and tweets are just the text of historical tweets.

A reason why the authors do not provide the datasets in their GitHub Repository is, that researchers need a specific license to use the data for academic purposes. The alternative of scrapping data from Twitter (now X) is not available, since accessing the data is only allowed after API access is granted. Also, data from social media platforms must be heavily anonymized to protect individuals from being identified from the dataset.

4 Workflow and Code Changes

Upon a thorough examination of the initial report, all accessible materials, and the challenges encountered, we embraced the subsequent workflow. In the GitHub, the authors state that the code was tested with TensorFlow 1.11.0, Python2, and Python3 (predominantly with Python2). Therefore, our initial plan was to try running the code in Google Colab and on our PCs and then compare the obtained results. The first encountered problem was the inability to run the code in Google Colab as it does not support TensorFlow 1.XX versions. Eventually, we solved the problem with TensorFlow by using a virtual environment.

Further investigation showed that there was a merge conflict in code files (`metric.py`, `parameter_attention_pos_twitter.py`, and `utils.py`). The conflicts were resolved by correcting syntax discrepancies in the mentioned files. Afterwards, it turned out that the models for BERT and Chinese BERT were

missing. However, the Chinese BERT model was not necessary because the sample data was for Twitter only. Also, the code incorporated problems such as missing files (`parameter_attention_twitter`) and incorrect namings. Issues were resolved by correcting the import statements, renaming, and updating paths accordingly.

The next step is the creation of `data_split.py`, which intends to split the sample dataset into training, validation, and test sets using an 80/10/10 ratio. The script employs the `train_test_split` function from the `sklearn.model_selection` module to achieve this partitioning. The first split separates the data into training and a combined validation-test set (`val_test`), while the second split further divides `val_test` into distinct validation and test sets. To neatly organize the split data, the script creates directories named `train`, `val`, and `test` within the `sample_data` directory. Each of these directories contains pickle files storing `ids`, `labels`, `one_hot_labels`, and `texts`. The script concludes by printing a success message, indicating that the data split and saving process was completed successfully.

Upon running `python data_split.py`, the data split was successful. However, subsequent attempts to execute `PRED.py` resulted in tracebacks, specifically related to the dimensions mismatch during concatenation in the `load_input_att.py` file. The errors indicated that the input array dimensions for the concatenation axis must match exactly, but there was a mismatch in size between the arrays at index 0 (has size 172823) and index 1 (has size 172824). These issues need further investigation and resolution to proceed with the workflow. Currently, we are stuck at the To Do part in the `PRED.py` script, as it is written in Chinese and translation suggests to concatenate the history, however there is not enough information provided on the further steps. The vast majority of files (`PRED.py`, `create_input.py`, `load_input_att.py`, `matric.py`, `parameter_attention_twitter.py`, `utils.py`) included repetitions of the same code twice, most probably caused by Git commit. Besides that, files included naming inconsistencies, namely there was a `parameter_attention_pos_twitter.py` file, but in another section, it was imported as `parameter_attention_twitter` (in `load_input_att.py`, `'from parameter_attention_twitter import *'` was commented out and replaced with `'from parameter_attention_pos_twitter import *'`). Also, as the sample data was provided only for Twitter, there was no point in keeping the Weibo part of the code (this can be found in `PRED.py`). Even though we found both of the BERT models (English and Chinese), in case we were provided Weibo's sample data or a full dataset from the creators. In that manner you can find all changes in the code, as we kept the initial code lines as comments and added the modified one right after.

5 Conclusion

Reproducing the experiments proposed in the paper proved to be a challenge due to faulty code, missing files, lack of documentation on how to use their code

and missing descriptions of the used libraries and versions. Even though we tried to fix the code and run it, we still would not get the same results as only Twitter's sample data was provided and that is not enough to reproduce the original paper.

References

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